

MODELLING AND CHARACTERIZATION OF THICKNESS VARIATIONS IN L-SHAPE OUT-OF-AUTOCLAVE LAMINATES

M. Brillant and P. Hubert*

Department of Mechanical Engineering, McGill University, Montréal, Canada

* Corresponding author (pascal.hubert@mcgill.ca)

1 Introduction

With recent advancements in out-of-autoclave material technology and manufacturing techniques, there is a growing interest for the manufacturing of larger and more complex, integrated composite structures for the aerospace industry. The manufacturing of complex shape composite laminates has been studied widely for autoclave-cured prepreg materials [1-4]. Although an increasing number of references exist in the literature on the study of out-of-autoclave composite laminates, most of these studies have been performed on flat laminates [5-8].

A recurring challenge in the manufacturing of complex shape composite laminates is the variation in thickness along the geometry [1-4]. It was shown that the thickness variation is localized at the corner and is a function of tool shape, material, lay-up, laminate thickness, and corner radius. Corner thickening was observed for laminates manufactured over concave (female) tools. In the case of convex (male) tools, both corner thinning and corner thickening was noted, depending on the fibre direction and bleed conditions [1, 3-4]. Hubert et al. [1] proposed an explanation for the variation of thickness based on a free-body diagram analysis of the stresses at the corner. For equilibrium of forces, the reaction stresses from the tool are not equal to the normal stresses applied to the laminate due to the difference in surface area between the pressure side and the tool side at the corner.

Although the effect of various processing and geometrical parameters on the thickness variation at the corner is understood, no clear relation has been developed to help in the design of complex shape laminates. This paper presents the details of an analytical model of the compaction of L-shape laminates, developed to predict the thickness variation at the corner. Also, an experimental study was performed to characterize the thickness variation at the corner of L-shape laminates

manufactured with out-of-autoclave prepreg as a function of laminate thickness and corner radius. From these results, guidelines for the design of L-shape out-of-autoclave laminates will be established.

2 Analytical Model

2.1 Free-Body Diagram Analysis

An analytical model of the compaction of an L-shape laminate over concave and convex tools was developed based on the free-body diagram analysis of the corner section, as illustrated in Figures 1 and 2. For simplification, the model assumed a symmetric deformation and no resistance to laminate shear, which implied that the laminate plies were free to slip. This assumption allowed stresses parallel to the tool surface to be neglected and the effect of fibre direction was then ignored. In addition, a perfectly elastic fibre bed compaction behaviour was considered, neglecting viscous effects. The effect of the material was captured through the bulk factor, representing the ratio between the prepreg final thickness after processing and the initial prepreg thickness.

Consider the corner section of a laminate over a concave tool, as illustrated in Fig. 1, where t is the flange final thickness, t_c is the thickness at the corner and R is the tool corner radius. The applied pressure P acts on the bag surface S_p and the tool reaction pressure $P_{avgtool}$ acts on tool surface S_T . From equilibrium of forces at the corner section, the ratio of pressure stresses for a concave tool $(P_{avgtool}/P)_{CC}$ are related following Eq. (1).

$$(P_{avgtool}/P)_{CC} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{2}[(R/t - 1) + (1 + \sqrt{2})\Delta t/t]}{\frac{\pi}{2}R/t + (2 + 2\sqrt{2})\Delta t/t} \quad (1)$$

with $\Delta t = t_c - t$. Similarly, the ratio of pressure stresses at the corner of a laminate over a convex

tool, $(P_{avgtool}/P)_{cv}$, as illustrated in Fig. 2, can be expressed as follows:

$$(P_{avgtool}/P)_{cv} = \frac{\frac{\pi}{2}[(R/t + 1) - (1 + \sqrt{2})\Delta t/t]}{\frac{\pi}{2}R/t - (2 + 2\sqrt{2})\Delta t/t} \quad (2)$$

Under out-of-autoclave (OOA) pressure conditions (i.e. <100kPa), the non-linear stiffening behavior of the fibre bed compaction can be neglected and the stress-strain relation is approximately linear [9]; i.e. $\sigma = k \cdot \varepsilon$, where σ is the normal stress, ε the normal strain and k a coefficient of proportionality. Thus, the ratio of normal stresses can then be related to the ratio of strain between the corner and the flange. Also, in defining the bulk factor c_1 as the ratio of the flange initial thickness to the flange final thickness, the ratio of pressure stresses at the corner can be expressed as a function of the bulk factor c_1 and the thickness variation Δt , as illustrated by Eq. (3).

$$\frac{P_{avgtool}}{P} = \frac{c_1 - (\Delta t/t + 1)}{c_1 - 1} \quad (3)$$

Combining Eq. (1) and (2) with Eq. (3), the model results in an expression for the predicted thickness variation at the corner (Δt) as a function of the design laminate thickness (t) and corner radius (R) for concave (Δt_{cc}) and convex (Δt_{cv}) laminates, see Eq. (4) and Eq. (5) respectively.

$$\Delta t_{cc} = t * \left\{ \frac{\left[\left(\frac{4}{\pi} - 1 \right) A - R/t \right] + \sqrt{\left[\left(\frac{4}{\pi} - 1 \right) A - R/t \right]^2 + \frac{16}{\pi} A}}{\frac{8}{\pi} (1 + \sqrt{2})} \right\} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta t_{cv} = t * \left\{ \frac{\left[\left(\frac{4}{\pi} - 1 \right) A + R/t \right] - \sqrt{\left[\left(\frac{4}{\pi} - 1 \right) A + R/t \right]^2 + \frac{16}{\pi} A}}{\frac{8}{\pi} (1 + \sqrt{2})} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where $A = (c_1 - 1) * (1 + \sqrt{2})$

2.2 Thickness Variation Predictions

The model described by Eqs. (4) and (5) suggests that the thickness variation at the corner is a function of the thickness of the laminate and the radius-to-thickness ratio. Figures 3 and 4 illustrate maps of the predicted thickness variation for various radius-to-thickness ratios of concave and convex laminates obtained by solving Eqs. (4) and (5) respectively. The bulk factor c_1 was 1.2, which corresponds to the average calculated value of the laminates manufactured for the experimental study discussed in section 3. The results are plotted for the constant radius curves of 5, 10 and 15 mm. The thin black

lines represent the constant thickness curves of 2, 3 and 4 mm. A positive value for thickness variation indicates corner thickening.

The model predicts corner thickening for concave laminates and corner thinning for convex laminates. For both laminate shapes, larger thickness variations are predicted for smaller values of radius-to-thickness ratio (R/t). Using the model described by Eqs. (4) and (5), a designer can build a map similar to those of Figures 3 and 4 with desired corner radius curves or thickness curves. For a given acceptable amount of thickness variation, the corresponding critical radius-to-thickness ratio for design can be determined.

3 Experimental Investigation

3.1 Objective

The objective of the experimental study was to characterize the thickness variation at the corner based on the radius-to-thickness ratio of L-shape laminates. The study was performed for two material forms: Cytec Cycom 5320 PW and 8HS OOA prepregs. A total of 10 concave and 10 convex L-shape laminates of various radius-to-thickness ratio (R/t) were manufactured with each prepreg.

3.2 Manufacturing of the Laminates

All laminate specimens had 57 mm in flange length and 100 mm in width. Two concave and two convex tools were used with corner radius of 9.53 mm and 12.7 mm. The laminate thicknesses were chosen to cover a wide range of R/t , from 1.43 to 6.96 for the concave laminates and from 0.85 to 3.42 for the convex laminates.

The plies were stacked with a $[0^\circ]$ lay-up. The PW prepreg had a lower fibre aerial density (195 g/m² [10]) in comparison with the 8HS prepreg (370 g/m² [10]), making it easier to drape. Also, the cured ply thickness of the PW prepreg was almost half that of the 8HS prepreg. The number of plies was then adjusted to provide the desired laminate thickness. After every set of four plies, the laminate was debulked at room temperature for 10 minutes. Both materials showed a similar bulk factor.

An edge breathing set-up was placed along each edge after trimming. The laminate was covered with non-perforated release film and breather material. A vacuum-bag was sealed around the set-up and vacuum pressure was applied. To prevent vacuum-bag bridging, pleats were done with the bag at

multiple locations. The part was cured in an oven following a two-step cure cycle; starting with a 2-hour debulk at room temperature, followed by a ramp at 2.8°C/min to a first dwell temperature of 93°C. A second ramp at 1.7°C/min follows up to a dwell temperature of 143°C. The dwell times were adjusted to account for the lag in temperature of the laminate and ensure laminate temperature dwell times of 2 hours each.

After processing, the part was cut at two locations to provide one specimen of 100 mm width with two surfaces available for analysis. The surfaces of cut were polished up to 600-grit with silicone-carbide waterproof sandpaper and then scanned at a resolution of 1200 dpi. Thickness measurements were performed by image analysis at nine locations on each surface of cut, as illustrated in Fig. 5. The results are presented in terms of average thickness variation for each specimen. The thickness variation was calculated for each surface of cut as the difference between the thickness measurement at the corner (location 5) and the average of the thickness measurements along the flange (locations 1 to 3 and 7 to 9).

3.3 Results of Concave Laminates

The average thickness variations for the PW and 8HS laminates as a function of the radius-to-thickness ratio (R/t) for the concave tool are illustrated in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, respectively. The error bar indicates the maximum and minimum distribution of thickness variation calculated for each specimen. The experimental results for concave laminates confirmed the observations found in the literature: with increasing laminate thickness and decreasing tool corner radius, the thickness variation was increased.

Similar trends were observed for both materials. However, the material had a clear effect on the magnitude of the thickness variation. In fact, the 8HS concave laminates showed almost twice as much thickening than the PW laminates. This is believed to be due to a lower ability of the 8HS laminate to undergo laminate shear. Given the larger thickness per ply of the 8HS prepreg, less plies were used for the same laminate thickness. This reduces the number of available interfaces for interply shear.

The predicted thickness variations from the analytical model are also presented in the figures for each tool corner radius and showed good agreement with the experimental results for the PW concave laminates. For the 8HS laminates, the model

underestimated the thickness variation. This indicates that the assumption for free laminate shear may not hold for the 8HS prepreg.

3.4 Results of Convex Laminates

The experimental results for the thickness variation at the corner of the PW and 8HS convex laminates are presented in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 respectively. The predicted thickness variations from the analytical model are also presented in the figures. The convex laminates showed corner thickening as opposed to corner thinning predicted by the model. The thickness variation increased with decreasing R/t , similarly to the concave laminates. However, the magnitudes of the thickness variations were lower than those for the concave laminates. Also, the material demonstrated very little effect on the measurements.

It is believed that corner thickening was obtained for the convex laminates due to the presence of edge breathing at the edges. Consider a typical laminate edge after compaction as illustrated in Fig. 10. It can be observed that the compaction stress at the corner (σ_p) caused the laminate to shear away from the corner. Also, some interply shear stresses may have developed in reaction to the compaction (τ). However, the edge breathing clearly opposed laminate shear (σ_{cb}). The fibres oriented in the hoop direction were then loaded in compression and opposed the compaction at the corner, resulting in corner thickening. Given this boundary condition, the analytical model assumption for free laminate shear does not hold. In addition, the shear deformation should increase with increasing material bulk factor. Hence, the boundary conditions cannot be neglected in the compaction of materials with high bulk factors.

4 Conclusions

For the materials used, the experimental results can be used to determine a critical radius-to-thickness ratio for design (R/t) based on a given acceptable limit of thickness variation for Cytec Cycom 5320 PW and 8HS OOA prepreps. Also, larger corner thickening resulted for the 8HS concave laminates in comparison to the PW laminates. The high bulk factor of the materials considered, in combination with the presence of edge breathing along the edges of the laminates, caused corner thickening for the convex laminates. The analytical model predictions

showed good agreement with the PW concave laminate experimental results.

Acknowledgements

This research was conducted with the financial support from Bombardier Aerospace, Bell Helicopter Textron Canada, Delastek Inc., the Consortium for Research and Innovation in Aerospace in Québec (CRIAQ), the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC). The authors would like to acknowledge the contribution and support of M. Philip Barsalou for the manufacturing of the experimental samples. The authors also thank graduate students James Kratz, Timotei Centea and research assistant Loleï Khoun for their discussions and suggestions.

References

- [1] P. Hubert and A. Poursartip "Aspects of the compaction of composite angle laminates: An experimental investigation". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 35, No. 1, pp 2-26, 2001
- [2] G. Fernlund, J. Griffith, R. Courdji and A. Poursartip "Experimental and numerical study of the effect of caul-sheets on corner thinning of composite laminates". *Composites Part A*, Vol. 33, No. 3, pp 411-426, 2002
- [3] Y. Li, M. Li, Y. Gu and Z. Zhan "Numerical and experimental study on the effect of lay-up type and structural elements on thickness uniformity of L-shaped laminates". *Applied Composite Materials*, Vol. 16, No. 2, pp 101-115, 2009
- [4] M. Li and C.L. Tucker "Modeling and simulation of two-dimensional consolidation for thermoset matrix composites". *Composites Part A*, Vol. 33, No. 6, pp 877-892, 2002
- [5] L. Repecka and J. Boyd "Vacuum-Bag-Only-Curable Prepregs That Produce Void-Free Parts". In: *Proceedings of 47th International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition*. Long Beach, May, 2002. p.1862-1874
- [6] V. Michaud, S.S. Tavares, A. Sigg, S. Lavanchy and J.-A. Manson "Low Pressure Processing of High Fiber Content Composites". In: *Proceedings of FPCM8*. Douai, July, 2006
- [7] C. Ridgard "Out of Autoclave Composite Technology for Aerospace, Defense, and Space Structures". In: *Proceedings of 53th International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition*. Baltimore, May, 2009
- [8] G.G. Bond, J.M. Griffith and G. Hahn "A Study of Non-Autoclave Prepreg Manufacturing Technology". *SAMPE Journal*, Vol. 45, pp 6-19, 2009

- [9] M. Brilliant "Out-of-Autoclave Manufacturing of Complex Shape Composite Laminates". M.Eng Thesis, McGill University, 2011
- [10] CYCOM® 5320 Toughened Epoxy for Structural Applications Out-of-Autoclave Manufacturing. Cytec Industries Inc., Product Information. 24 Aug. 2010. <<http://www.cytec.com/engineered-materials/Products/CYCOM%205320.htm>>

Fig.1. Free-body diagram of the corner section of a laminate over a concave tool after compaction.

Fig.2. Free-body diagram of the corner section of a laminate over a convex tool after compaction.

Fig.3. Concave tool – Constant radius curves of the predicted thickness variations for various R/t .

Fig.6. Experimental thickness variation (mm) and model predictions (mm) for PW concave laminates.

Fig.4. Convex tool – Constant radius curves of the predicted thickness variations for various R/t .

Fig.7. Experimental thickness variation (mm) and model predictions (mm) for 8HS concave laminates.

Fig.5. Thickness measurement locations

Fig.8. Experimental thickness variation (mm) and model predictions (mm) for PW convex laminates.

Fig.9. Experimental thickness variation (mm) and model predictions (mm) for 8HS convex laminates.

Fig.10. Close view of the end of an 8HS convex laminate. The plies moved upwards in reaction to the opposing stresses.